

The Impact of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Motivation in Indonesia Technology Startup Companies Post Pandemic Covid 19

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ABSTRACT: Covid 19 poses significant challenges for Indonesian technology start-ups. Beginning with shifts in work modes, unstable global conditions, and geopolitics. This has caused many businesses to lay off employees, which can negatively impact employee motivation and perceptions of the organization. Perceived organizational support and motivation are crucial factors to consider in this circumstance, as the startup industry in Indonesia is rapidly growing and positively impacting the economy. This study presents an overview of the current state of perceived organizational support, autonomous motivation, and controlled motivation among employees of technology startups. It also investigates the effect of perceived organizational support on autonomous and controlled motivation among employees in Indonesian technology startups, which can be beneficial knowledge for startup practitioners. This study's respondents involve 279 employees from Indonesian technology startups. Its analysis employs a simple linear regression method. The findings show that among employees at technology startups, perceived organizational support significantly affects autonomous motivation but has no significant effect on controlled motivation.

KEYWORDS: Autonomous Motivation, Controlled Motivation, Perceived Organizational Support (POS), Work Motivation, Startup.

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic has had an impact on all sectors of the domestic economy, including technology startups, 83.5% of technology companies were affected, 51.7% experienced adverse effects (Katadata, 2020). The conditions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic compelled businesses to make adjustments to their work arrangements. Employees experience the precipitous transformation of a work system as a result of Covid-19; from on-site work to remote work from home to hybrid work, with a low level of trust concerning the company's operational implementation preparedness (Cisco, 2022). Also, as a result of unstable global macroeconomics and geopolitical conflicts, numerous startups laid off workers at the end of the previous year (Pertwi, 2022; Damara, 2022; Dewi, 2022). These conditions weaken employees' confidence in their ability to maintain employment (Liu, 2022) and may make employees of startups experience uncertainty and feel uncomfortable, which could lead to negative perception of the organization.

The relationship between employee adaptability and perceptions of uncertainty over change is mediated by perceived organizational support (Cullen et al., 2014). Perceived organizational support refers to the manner in which employees construct a broad view of the degree to which their employer appreciates their contribution, provides suitable resources, and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). The development of a favorable opinion of the support received by employees from their organization will result in beneficial consequences for both the employees and the business. Employees who do not perceive supported by their organization may limit their effort, leading to reduced levels of performance and reporting more unfavorable job attitudes (Cullen et al., 2014).

Eder & Eisenberger (2008) convey employees generate a sense of responsibility to actively work toward the achievement of organizational goals as a result of their perception of support from the organization. In a working environment a drive to devote employee abilities to performance is created by employee's motivation. A motivated employee will strive to achieve a work-related goal (Mahmoud et al., 2021). In line with these statements, Gillet et al. (2013) states that organizational support is one of the factors associated with work motivation.

Work motivation is the intensity with which an individual attempts to work hard and effectively—the excitement, focus, and persistence of efforts in the workplace (Golembiewski, 2001). The self-determination theory classifies motivation as either

controlled or autonomous. Being autonomous entails having the ability to make decisions and acting with volition. In contrast, controlled motivation is characterized by a sense of obligation and pressure to engage in the behaviors (Gagné & Deci, 2005).

A study on police officers demonstrated that perceived organizational support increases self-determination motivation (Gillet et al., 2013). In a more recent study on self-initiated expatriates, perceived organizational support in finances is positively related to controlled motivation, while support in careers and adjustments is positively related to autonomous motivation (Chen & Shaffer, 2017). In addition, Gagné et al. (2010) and Gillet et al. (2013) found that perceived organizational support has positive connections with autonomous and controlled motivation.

The majority of studies on perceived organizational support were conducted prior to the Covid-19 pandemic. The existing working environment and conditions have shifted. Meanwhile, Indonesia's startup growth is growing; according to the e-Conomy SEA (2021) report by Google, Temasek, and Bain & Company, Indonesia's digital economy would be worth US\$146 billion by 2025. Indonesia is ranked fifth in the globe in terms of the number of start-ups (Toewoeh, 2022). Employees have emerged as a valuable company asset in the current era (Kossivi et al., 2016); therefore, businesses that want to improve employee well-being and performance must invest in gaining a comprehension of their employees' work motivation (Klotz, 2020). Previous research has shown that performance is positively correlated with high levels of perceived organizational support (Kurtessis et al., 2017; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Therefore, in order for a business to provide appropriate, useful and effective support to its employees, it is important for the company to know the present situation of the employees and understand the impact that perceived organizational support has on each type of motivation, autonomous motivation and controlled motivation. The results of this study can provide knowledge that can be applied in formulating and developing company regulations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation theories are diverse and difficult to categorize. There is no theory that able comprehensively explains motivation, but every perspective contributes to a well-developed understanding of motivation, its contributing factors, and results. Motivation is understood as the extent to which a person is moved or intrigued to try to pursue a goal. Whereas, work motivation refers to the extent to which a person strives to work hard and effectively – the excitement, direction and persistence of efforts in the work environment (Golembiewski, 2001). In the present research, the researcher adopts self-determination theory's concept of motivation to analyze the situation.

Self-Determination Theory

Self-determination theory is a psychological concept that explains the importance of motivation in human behavior across different contexts, including the workplace (Vallerand et al., 2008; Ryan & Deci, 2017). It is particularly interested in the ways in which social-contextual elements either support or prevent the well-being of individuals by addressing their fundamental psychological demands for competence, relatedness, and autonomy (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Individuals may have a wide range of motivations from amotivation or an unwillingness to take action all the way up to an active personal commitment or passive compliance.

This theory emphasizes the development and maintenance of autonomous motivation and self-regulation, distinguishing different types of motivation along a continuum from controlled to autonomous (Ryan & Deci, 2017). They are distinct in terms of the underlying regulatory processes and experiences that are linked with them, and it is possible to categorize behaviors according to the degree to which they are autonomous or controlled. An action that has intrinsic motivation is when an individual is experiencing volition, self-originating, and having the sense of choice, understood as autonomous by definition. On the other hand, controlled motivation involves a feeling of pressure and a sense of having to participate in the activities (Gagne & Deci, 2005; Ryan & Deci, 2017). Extrinsically motivated behaviors might vary greatly in terms of how much they are controlled versus autonomous. Depending on how much a regulation is internalized, it can be wholly or partially controlled from the outside or inside (Gagné et al., 2010). Extrinsic motivation can thus be identified into four types, external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation, and integrated regulation (Ryan & Deci, 2020).

Controlled forms of motivation consist of external regulation and introjected regulation. As a form of motivation, external regulation is frequently interpreted as controlled and non-autonomous due to the fact that it is launched and maintained by elements from the external setting. It is influenced by the benefits and consequences that are imposed from the outside. Introjected regulation is that which an individual has internalized but not fully accepted. Behaviour is controlled by the promise of positive

self-perception upon achievement and the fear of negative emotions like embarrassment, shame, or guilt in the event of a failure (Gagné & Deci, 2005; Ryan & Deci, 2020).

Motivation that is autonomous is represented by identified and integrated regulation. Individuals with identified regulations have a high level of volition or willingness to act. They recognize or personally support the value of the activity. Integrated regulation is the most autonomous form of extrinsic motivation. This is when a person not only acknowledges and recognizes the importance of the activity, but also believes that it is consistent with their other main interests and values. Both of these regulations are supported by a sense of value, which means that a person sees an activity based on its value even if it is not necessarily enjoyable for them. There is also autonomous extrinsic motivation that differ from intrinsic motivation, which is based on interest and pleasure. People are motivated to do activity because they find the action fascinating and enjoyable (Ryan & Deci, 2020).

In the working context, Gagné and Deci (2005) postulate that work motivation is influenced by personal and situational factors. Personality traits like optimism and deeply established causal orientations are examples of personal factors that may affect how people respond to situations and events that are related to their work (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Situational factors in organization include how work is distributed, arranged and designed, also the quality of interactions with managers, colleagues, subordinates, and customers (Gagné & Forest, 2008).

This research wants to see the condition of the motivation of employees working in startup technology companies post the Covid-19 condition and the layoff. This theory provides a multidimensional understanding of motivation that allows for the assessment of motivational level and motivational type (Gagné et al., 2010). Not only look at the source of motivation, intrinsic or extrinsic. Instead, this research wants to see employee motivation based on the fundamentals of the regulatory process and also the associations of their experience, where motivation is seen from an autonomous-controlled continuum, distinguished into autonomous and controlled motivation (Gagne & Deci, 2005; Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support is defined as "an employee's perception that the organization values his or her work contributions and cares about the employee's well-being" (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Eisenberger et al., 2016). Employees form global perceptions of how much their contributions are valued and how deeply the organization cares about their well-being, leading to increased levels of perceived organizational support (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Eisenberger et al., 2016). The perceived organizational support influences both employer and employee effort-outcome expectations. It drives up employee's expectation that their company would compensate them for making an extra effort towards achieving its goals. The way employees are treated reflects their impressions about their organization's attitude toward them. Those who work in an organization that values their efforts and cares about their well-being likely to perform better (Eisenberger et al., 1986).

Perceived organizational support gives employees a simple way to understand how they are valued by the company. This can range from the perception that the company views them favourably to the opposite extreme (Eisenberger et al., 2016). It also can be seen as a form of social exchange, where employees perceive that they are receiving support from their employers, feel more devoted to the company, more content with their work, and more willing to go above and beyond the job scope as a result (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002).

A variety of important employee outcomes, including job satisfaction, commitment to the organization, intention to leave their present employment, and job performance, are strongly correlated with perceived organizational support. Studies have indicated when employees experience better organizational support, they report improved levels of satisfaction with their work and commitment to the office (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017). Meanwhile, employees who perceive less organizational support tend to have greater levels of intention to leave the company and workers tend to perform better on the job when they perceive higher levels of organizational support (Eisenberger et al., 1986). These findings indicate that perceived organizational support is related to some crucial employee outcomes for organizations. Therefore, researchers want to explore how perceived organizational support affects employee work motivation in technology startup organizations, particularly after went through pandemic Covid-19 and followed by layoff situations.

Startup

There are numerous definitions of startup in various publications. Each definition emphasizes a characteristic of a startup, but these definitions define similar characteristics. Ries (2011) defined startup as a company that has just been established and is still

experiencing a development phase, that is built to create new products or services in conditions of high uncertainty. It emphasizes that startups operate in an uncertain environment, and that they use lean and agile methodologies to rapidly iterate and pivot their business models as needed. Innovation, digitalization, novel technologies, and disruptive business models are frequently linked to startups. Moreover, a startup is also defined as “a temporary organization in search of a scalable, repeatable, profitable business model” (Blank & Dorf, 2012). This definition emphasizes the primary goal of startups: to develop a sustainable and scalable business model capable of generating significant revenue and growth over time. Meanwhile, Bastié et al. (2013) define startup as a setting up of new means of production. Startup is also understood as privately-held, innovation and high-tech driven small-to-medium-sized enterprises with less than ten years of existence that are dedicated to exploring and building sustainable and scalable business models (Men et al., 2021). It may generally be apprehended that startups are characterized by a focus on innovation, high-tech driven, scalability and rapid growth in the face of uncertainty.

Perceived Organizational Support with Autonomous and Controlled Motivation

Multiple research initiatives have been carried out with the aim of determining the connection that exists between perceived organizational support and autonomous and controlled motivation. Research has consistently shown that a favorable association exists between perceived organizational support and autonomous motivation (Gagné et al., 2010; Gillet et al., 2013; Lopes et al., 2019). Moreover, studies also discovered that autonomous motivation is a moderator between perceived organizational support with job autonomy, and work outcomes (Galletta et al., 2016) also a mediator with workers' well-being (Lopes et al., 2019). Controlled motivation study, on the other hand, yields inconclusive outcomes. According to study, perceived organizational support correlates to controlled motivation (Gagné et al., 2010; Gillet et al., 2013). There are, however, research that reveal no association between perceived organizational support and controlled motivation (Galletta et al., 2016; Lopes et al., 2019).

Those researches were done before the Covid-19 pandemic. Pandemic Covid-19 changed many things and had a significant impact on businesses in various sectors. One of them is a technology startup company which is currently growing rapidly and making a major contribution to the Indonesian economy (Toewoeh, 2022). Employees had to experience changes in working arrangement with low company readiness. In addition, in the second half of 2022, unstable global economic conditions and geopolitical conflicts caused numerous startup companies to lay off (Pertiwi, 2022; Damara, 2022; Dewi, 2022). These conditions cause the employees to feel less confident in their abilities to keep their jobs (Liu, 2022). Thus, this research wants to see how the condition of perceived organizational support and employee motivation in technology startup companies after facing the Covid-19 pandemic and layoffs that occurred.

Research questions based on the given explanation are as follows:

1. How's the condition of perceived organizational support among employees who work in technology startup companies?
2. How's the work motivation condition among employees who work in technology startup companies?
3. Is there any impact of perceived organizational support to autonomous motivation in employees who work in technology startup companies?
4. Is there any impact of perceived organizational support to controlled motivation in employees who work in technology startup companies?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following are the hypotheses that will be tested:

1. Ha1: There's a significant effect of perceived organizational support to autonomous motivation among employees at technology startup companies.
H01: There's no significant effect of perceived organizational support to autonomous motivation among employees at technology startup companies
2. Ha2: There's a significant effect of perceived organizational support to controlled motivation among employees at technology startup companies.
H02: There's no significant effect of perceived organizational support to controlled motivation among employees at technology startup companies.

METHODOLOGY

Sample and Procedure.

Data collection was carried out using questionnaire that distributed online on various social media platforms. Non-random sampling was employed for this study. The characteristics requirements for respondents to be included in this research are:

1. A full-time employee
A full-time employee is a person who works a set amount of hours established by their company, on a permanent basis or a fixed term contract.
2. Currently working in a technology startup company which has been established for more than 2 years
Companies must have been established for more than 2 years because the phenomenon that this research wants to see is employees at startup companies who have experienced the Covid-19 pandemic and went through layoff conditions at the end of 2022.

This study uses descriptive statistics and linear regression for data processing and analysis methods. Classical assumption tests also conducted as prior testing of simple linear regression, it includes the normality test, linearity test, and heteroscedasticity test.

Measure

There are two instrument that used in this research, which are the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) developed by Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchinson and Sowa (1986) and the Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS) developed by Gagné, Forest, Vansteenkiste, Crevier-Braud, Broeck, Aspeli, Bellerose, Benabou, Chemolli, Güntert, Halvari, Indiyastuti, Johnson, Molstad, Naudin, Ndao, Olafsen, Roussel, Wang, and Westbye (2015). The Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) consists of 36 items. The Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS) has 19 items, consists of three domains, amotivation, extrinsic motivation, and intrinsic motivation. The extrinsic motivation is divided into 4 sub-domains: external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation and integrated regulation. The data gathered will be processed using a higher-order approach, only two domains will be calculated in this study: autonomous motivation and controlled motivation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of data processing which will be presented are collected from 279 respondents.

Demographic data of the respondents.

Sex	Educational Background	Working Mode
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Male: 113 (40.5%)• Female: 166 (59.5%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• High School/Vocational High School/and equivalent: 11 (3.9%)• Diploma - D1/D2/D3:12 (4.3%)• Bachelor - S1/D4: 198 (71.0%)• Magister - S2 and further professional education: 58 (21.8%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Remote working: 75 (26.9%)• Work from office: 60 (21.5%)• Hybrid or combination of remote and work from office: 144 (51.6%)
Range of Age	Employment Status	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• < 26 years old: 62 (22.2%)• 26 - 41 years old: 210 (75.3%)• 42 - 57 years old: 6 (2.2%)• > 57 years old: 1 (0.4%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Permanent: 223 (79.9%)• Contract:56 (20.1%)	
Marital Status	Length of Tenure in The Company	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Single: 163 (58.4%)• Married:115 (41.2%)• Divorce:1 (0.4%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• < 1 year: 48 (17.2%)• 1-3 years: 166 (59.5%)• > 3 years: 65 (23.3%)	

Descriptive of Respondents' Perceived Organizational Support

This study categorizes perceived organizational support into high, moderate and low based on the mean score and standard deviation. Scores that are categorized as low are scores < 86,32, moderate $86,32 \geq 114,78$, and high > 114,78. The result show that 31 (11,1%) had a low perceived organizational support. As many as 211 (75.6%) perceived moderate organizational support,

while 37 (13.3%) perceived high organizational support. The majority of responders rate organizational support as being in the moderate range.

Descriptive of Respondents' Work Motivation

- *Autonomous Motivation.* This study categorizes controlled motivation into high, moderate and low based on the mean score and standard deviation. Scores that are categorized as low are scores $< 16,19$, moderate $16,19 \geq 22,49$, and high $> 22,49$. The majority of respondents in this research, 46 (62,4%) had moderate autonomous motivation, followed by 59 (21,0%) who had high autonomous motivation and 46 (16,5%) respondents had a low level of autonomous motivation.
- *Controlled Motivation.* This study categorizes controlled motivation into high, moderate and low based on the mean score and standard deviation. Scores that are categorized as low are scores $< 26,66$, moderate $26,66 \geq 33,42$, and high $> 33,42$. There are 40 (14,3%) have a low level of controlled motivation. While the percentage of responders with moderate and high controlled motivation are 71,0% (198) and 14,7% (41).
- *Dominant Motivation.* To see overall the dominant motivation of the respondents, the researchers compared the mean scores obtained by each respondent. Motivation that has a higher score becomes a more dominant motivation, while those with the same score are categorized as balanced. The result shows that 9 had a balanced regulation of their autonomous and controlled motivation. There were 167 who were dominated by autonomous motivation and 103 who were dominated by controlled motivation. This demonstrates that the majority of responders have a dominance autonomous motivation.

Regression Analysis of Perceived Organizational Support on Autonomous Motivation & Controlled Motivation

The significance value of perceived organizational support on autonomous motivation is 0.000 (<0.05), implying that perceived organizational support has a significant effect on autonomous motivation. The regression equation is obtained $Y_1 = 10.233 + 0.091$. If the perceived organizational support variable increases by one unit on average, then the autonomous motivation variable also increases by 10,233. The variable perceived organizational support has a positive regression coefficient value of 0.091, which means that for each value added in perceived organizational support, the value of autonomous motivation will increase on average by 0.091. The value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) obtained is 0.167 (16.7%). This value indicates that 16.7% of the magnitude of autonomous motivation is influenced by perceived organizational support and the rest is influenced by other variables outside the study. Meanwhile, the significance value of perceived organizational support on controlled motivation is 0.084 (>0.05), implying that perceived organizational support has no effect on controlled motivation.

Discussions

The results of this study indicated employee perceived moderate organizational support in technology startup companies. Autonomous and controlled motivation are also moderate. Startup companies that rapidly iterate and pivot their business models to innovate may cause this (Ries, 2011). Startups ought to be ambidextrous to capitalize on their unique capabilities and explore new development prospects (O'Reilly III & Tushman, 2004). Companies need a strategy for supporting employees, which may not always be perceived as favorable. Ambidextrous encourages employees to strike a balance between exploitation and exploration (Müller et al., 2019). This may explain why startup employee motivation is moderate for autonomous and controlled. Startups need both motivations for ambidextrous employees.

Data analysis reveals a correlation between perceived organizational support and autonomous motivation. These findings are congruent with those of Gagne et al. (2010), Gillet et al. (2013), and Wu et al. (2022), who discovered that perceived organizational support influences workplace autonomy positively. Employees that feel supported and appreciated by the organization are more likely to take ownership of and participate in their work (Gagné & Deci, 2005). It is possible that this occurred because the employment and working environment matched their personal goals and beliefs. Autonomous motivation forms when external factors are integrated and aligned with personal ideals (Ryan & Deci, 2020). This survey's demographic data supports Sauermann (2018)'s argument that startup employees are more autonomously motivated.

Startup companies are small-to-medium enterprises (Men et al., 2021) that are still developing and employing lean and agile methods (Ries, 2011). Supervisors won't be able to micromanage employees due to limited resources and hybrid work environment. With limited resources, startups must maximize their value. Supervisors' autonomy support may be beneficial for startup work environments. Autonomy support involves supervisors recognizing and acknowledging subordinates, offering

important information in a non-manipulative manner, empowering, and providing choice. Working conditions with autonomy support encourage self-motivation (Baard et al, 2004). Furthermore, empowerment as part of autonomy support also has positive impact on employee motivation. Employee empowerment is a relational concept that outlines the way leaders share power, information, and resources with others. Empowering employees may satisfy their autonomy and competence needs, which positively impact autonomous motivation (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2015). It is in line with this study that demonstrates the majority of startup employee motivation being dominant in autonomous motivation.

This research found no correlation between perceived organizational support and controlled motivation. This is consistent with the findings of Galletta et al. (2016), who found no correlation between the two variables and no mediating effect of controlled motivation between perceptions of organizational support, job autonomy, and work results. However, these results differ from other studies which state that perceived organizational support is correlated with controlled motivation in the work context (Gagné et al., 2010; Gillet et al., 2013; Lopes et al., 2019).

Work motivation is influenced by personal and situational factors, such as how to work, division of labour and relationships with various parties in the workplace (Gagné & Deci, 2005). Employees in startup companies are more productive than employees in small and big established businesses. Compared to employees in large firms, startup employees are less concerned with external evaluations such as job security and salary, but more concerned with their autonomy such as independence, intellectual challenges and responsibility. They tend to be more autonomy motivated and less risk averse (Sauermaun, 2018). These characteristics may be one of the reasons there is no relationship between perceived organizational support and controlled motivation. External factors are less of a concern for startup employees and work motivation tends to come from within themselves.

The startup company environment is highly uncertain (Ries, 2011), lacks a culture, and is competitive, therefore supervisors must support employees. However, startup employees value independence and creative problem-solving more than job security (Sauermaun, 2018), therefore they are encouraged to take on greater responsibilities (Men et al., 2021). In addition, based on the data obtained, the majority of respondents currently work in hybrid mode. This working condition is certainly different from those who work in an office. Those who work hybrid are required independence, less monitoring, less control from supervisors. Therefore, the supervisor's role in doing close controlling work may not necessarily be seen as a form of support from the organization.

The majority of respondents from this study were in the age range of 26 -42 years or often called generation Y or millennials. Even though Millennials tend to be job hoppers, Millennials prioritize personal growth opportunities in choosing their jobs. Before taking on full responsibility, millennials must understand the significance and added value of their contributions to the work (Calk & Patrick, 2017). Millennials were found to be very loyal to organizations that they felt shared their values (Jerome et al., 2014). Their considerations that take into account personal matters and shared values show that they tend to carry out activities with the dominance of autonomous motivation. Because when activities are seen to be congruent with individual interests and values, activities that were previously regulated externally are already identified and integrated, forming autonomous motivation.

Controlled motivation means the motivation that involves a sense of pressure and a sense of having to participate in the acts. It consists of external regulation and introjected regulation. External regulation is a condition where a behavior is regulated externally, such as something done to avoid consequences. Meanwhile, the introjected regulation, even though the regulation has been assimilated by a person but has a controlling effect on the individual. These two regulations are in the initial process in the self-determination continuum and if the internalization process continues, it will advance to the next regulatory stage which is included in the autonomous-motivation categorization, identified regulation or integrated regulation (Gagné & Deci, 2005). As employee work activities take place, things that previously came from external regulations, over time and with the intensity of a behavior that is carried out might turn into autonomous motivation. Moreover, the characteristics of employees in startup companies tend to be more autonomous, so that things that are externally motivated may not be too much of a concern for them or may even be internalized so that they become part of employee autonomy.

Controlled motivation is part of a process that is influenced by external variables (Gagné & Deci, 2005), hence there are many aspects that might impact it. As a result, even if the organization provides support, there are various factors that may impact controlled motivation. Gagne et al., (2010) and Gillet et al., (2013) demonstrate that perceived organizational support is connected with controlled motivation; nonetheless, the results exceed their expectations, and this association has to be justified further.

Moreover, there are different results from one study to another. Therefore, re-justification and further research is needed on this issue.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn from data processing results about the effect of perceived organizational support on autonomous and controlled motivation in employees of technology startups:

1. The condition of the perceived organizational support of employees working in technology startup companies is in the moderate category. Perceptions in this medium category still cannot be concluded that the condition of perceptions of employee organizational support is good or not. Startup companies need to make further efforts to improve the support provided to employees to increase employees' perceived organizational support. Because employees believe that the treatment they have received, reflects the attitude that their organization has toward them.
2. The work motivation condition based on Self-determination theory in technology startup are both autonomous and controlled in moderate category. In technology startups, autonomous motivation is the main work motivation. Empowerment impacts employee autonomous motivation (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2015), which complements this result. Autonomous motivation is seen as better motivation, it improves job satisfaction, performance, and well-being, while controlled motivation causes burnout, lower job satisfaction, and poor performance (Gagné & Deci, 2005). Ambidextrous organization model also applies to motivation. Startup organizations ought to implement an ambidextrous organization since they rapidly change business models to innovate (Ries, 2011). To use ambidextrous contextually, organizations must balance exploitation and exploration, which needs people to create the right balance (Müller et al., 2019). In order to achieve balance in an organization, it requires with both employee with autonomous and controlled motivation. However, further research is needed to understand this condition more deeply.
3. Perceived organizational support significantly affects autonomous motivation. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. Even though this model is statistically significant, in terms of r square it is still only at 16.7%, which means that the rest is influenced by other variables outside the study. These results are in line with previous studies conducted by Gagne et al., (2010), Gillet et al., (2013), and Wu et al., (2022).
4. Perceived organizational support does not affect controlled motivation. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected. This demonstrates that the employees' perceived organizational support within startup companies does not have a substantial effect on controlled motivation for people working within those companies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations that follow can be used to develop future research and as input for practitioners in related fields.

1. The questionnaire was self-reported and distributed via several social media platforms. Assessment can be performed to have a better understanding.
2. To the best of my knowledge, there has been limited research examining the role of perceived organizational support in predicting worker motivation using self-determination theory. Therefore, this research can be replicated in different populations or expanded to enrich knowledge on this issue.
3. The Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS) was used in this study to assess motivation, with questions measuring autonomous motivation, controlled motivation, and amotivation. The amotivation elements were not used in this study. Amotivation is just as vital as motivation, thus it is supposed to be included and studied further in the future research.
4. Stakeholders in the technology startup industry should pay closer attention and try to discover organizational supports that impact on autonomous motivation.
5. Provide managerial positions with coaching training and establish a coaching culture to foster autonomous motivation.
6. Establishing standard operating procedures, policies, agreements and information that is clear and easily accessible to employees to provide procedural justice within the company.
7. Provide opportunities for employees to develop skills and competencies that will benefit their productivity and job performance.

- Organizing activities that foster relatedness in order to build relationships and connections among employees, particularly in technology startup companies that use remote or hybrid working.

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